

GREEN CULTURE AND INNOVATION: KEY DRIVERS OF FIRM PERFORMANCE IN PAKISTAN'S TEXTILE INDUSTRY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20813485>

Keywords

Green Innovation, Organizational Green Culture, Textile Firms' Performance, Green Human Capital, Green Supply Chain Management

Article History

Received: 28 October 2025

Accepted: 12 December 2025

Published: 26 December 2025

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Abstract

The current study examines the influence of green human capital (GHC) and green supply chain management (GSCM) on firm performance (FP) in Pakistan's textile sector. Using the natural resource-based view, this study explores the mediating role of green innovation (GI) and the moderating role of organizational green culture (OGC).

Design/methodology/approach – Data were collected from owners and managers of textile firms operating in Multan, Lahore, and Faisalabad through a structured questionnaire. A purposive sampling method was used to select participants with relevant knowledge and experience. Two hundred eighty-four (284) responses were analyzed using SmartPLS v4.1 to evaluate the study hypotheses.

Findings – Results confirm that GHC and GSCM enhance FP in the textile sector, both directly and indirectly via the mediating influence of GI. Moreover, OGC positively and significantly moderates the interaction among GHC, GSCM, and FP.

Practical implications – The results highlight the critical role of GI and OGC in enhancing FP. This study offers significant insights for textile firms in Pakistan to improve performance through green practices.

Originality/value – This research enhances the current literature by emphasizing the significance of GHC and GSCM concepts in achieving FP, while also underlining the critical roles of GI and OGC within textile firms in Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing industry significantly contributes to environmental concerns, including air and water pollution, wastage, and the depletion of natural resources, as well as climate change (Kraus et al., 2020; Zailani et al., 2012). As a result, it is crucial to consider eco-friendly practices, especially as economies are increasingly compelled to prioritize social and environmental issues amid industrialization. The increased focus on sustainability has led to the adoption of green initiatives in textile firms, small and medium-sized

enterprises (SMEs). Nowadays, firms must consider environmental impacts alongside profitability (Kraus et al., 2020) as stakeholders exert pressure to reduce the ecological impact of their manufacturing activities (Yu et al., 2017). An increasingly balanced approach to economic growth and environmental sustainability is required due to consumer preferences, resource constraints, and regulatory policies (Tang et al., 2018). So, Industrialists and academics are focusing on green aspects (Kraus et al., 2020). Green human capital (GHC) refers to a full stream

of knowledge, intangible abilities, and relations associated with environmental responsibility at individual and organizational levels. GHC often refers to intangible resources, considered more vital than tangible ones (Shoab et al., 2021). It can enhance environmentally friendly technologies (Khan et al., 2024) and also boost financial performance, economic growth, and sustainable development (Agyabeng-Mensah & Tang, 2021; Onubi et al., 2024). Several researchers have discovered a positive and significant link between the GHC and firm performance (FP) (Muafi et al., 2021a; Pratiwi et al., 2025), but Nureen et al. (2023a) revealed no significant relationship. It requires additional investigation. Green supply chain management (GSCM) reduces industrial operations' environmental impact and improves energy efficiency and collaboration with business partners. It also reduced waste and improved the company's green image and FP (Awan et al., 2017; Khan et al., 2021). GSCM is a critical issue for most businesses, especially in South Asia (Novitasari & Agustia, 2021). Manufacturers should implement GSCM practices in order to satisfy customer demand for sustainability (Liu et al., 2020). GSCM and FP relation is complicated. Recent research found significant positive relationships (Choi & Hwang, 2015a; Tarigan et al., 2021), and insignificant relationships (Nureen et al., 2023b). So, these relationships need to be clarified; it is imperative to undertake additional investigations into these mechanisms and to incorporate mediating factors. Green Innovation (GI) is a concept that helps reduce negative environmental impacts and increase FP to improve productivity, opportunities for market share, and public trust (Huang & Li, 2017; Song & Yu, 2018), improve existing products and technologies in order to attain sustainability (Hart & Dowell, 2011; Rehman et al., 2021; Shu et al., 2016). GI can achieve "win-win" outcomes by safeguarding the environment, increasing revenue (Awan et al., 2019; Shahzad et al., 2020), and minimizing resource utilization (Guo et al., 2021). The manufacturing sector must embrace GI to ensure sustainability (Fernando & Wah, 2017). Some researchers found positive associations between GI and GHC (Ni et al.,

2023), GI and GSCM (Nureen et al., 2023a), and GI and FP links (Maldonado-Guzmán et al., 2023; Tang et al., 2018). So, the study uses GI as a mediator between the GHC, GSCM, and FP relationships.

The importance of organizational green culture (OGC) is significant worldwide (Imran & Jingzu, 2022). Nowadays, OGC is essential for firms for success (Imran & Jingzu, 2022; Roscoe et al., 2019; Wang, 2019). Recent studies used OGC as a moderating variable (Akuma et al., 2025; Qu et al., 2022). The literature is almost silent on the moderating role of OGC in the associations among GHC, GSCM, and FP. So, the current study uses OGC as a moderator between the GHC, GSCM, and FP links. The variables being studied, such as GHC, GSCM, GI, OGC, have the potential to reduce pollution, protect the natural environment, and enhance firm performance. This study makes an ample contribution to the academic and research communities by advancing the theoretical development of the natural resource-based view theory (NRBVT). FP is an important research topic in the managerial and financial literature, and it is widely used as a dependent variable in business management (Asghar et al., 2020). Both the firm and society are affected by the firm's performance. Performance is essential for managers because it dictates how the organization achieves its vision, mission, and objectives (Samad, 2018). Economic objectives, manufacturing, and promotion can positively or negatively impact an organization's performance (Abeysekara et al., 2019; Halim et al., 2017).

The resource-based view (RBV) holds that firm's essential resources confer a competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). Hart (1995) recently introduced the NRBVT, an expansion of the RBV. This view holds that an internally focused approach is insufficient for competition due to ecological concerns. Hart (1995) stated that firms can gain a competitive advantage through proactive environmental practices. From the perspective of NRBVT, firms can enhance their performance and competitive advantage by their capacity to manage challenges associated with the natural environment (Hart & Dowell, 2011). Hart (1995) identifies several issues with the RBV theory. For

example, it breaks the link between the natural environment of a business and the business itself. Capabilities, pollution management, and environmental resources are critical to a business's success (Barney, 2000). Pollution prevention, product stewardship, and clean technology are three approaches to sustainability. We believe that the investigated variables have the potential to help textile manufacturing firms improve their environmental management, thereby increasing performance.

Pakistan's textile industry is selected because it is an important manufacturing sector. It is ninth in textile exports, fifth in production, and third in Asian cotton consumption. It is time to focus on the textile industry's green aspects to meet international standards. The Pakistani government has pledged to protect the environment and achieve carbon neutrality. According to certain studies (Adenle et al., 2015; Sharma et al., 2022), environmental hazards are more prevalent in developing nations. Consequently, firms in these countries need help in utilizing their resources. This study enhances our understanding by examining how the Pakistani textile industry leverages its green resources to achieve firm performance. This research is crucial as it addresses numerous knowledge gaps. **First**, the objective is to examine the direct impact that GHC and GSCM have on FP. **Second**: It investigates GI as a mediator in the relationship between GHC-FP and GSCM-FP. The study is concentrated on textile firms operating in Pakistan. **Third**: the moderating effect of OGC on the connection between GHC-FP and GSCM-FP is limited. Therefore, the use of OGC as a moderator in Pakistan's textile industry is an unprecedented development. **Furthermore**, this scholarly article analyzes the relationships using NRBVT.

2. Literature review and hypotheses development

2.1. Firms' Performance

Szilagi (1981) posits that FP comprises efficiency and effectiveness, which are the direct outcomes of the organization's internal activities. Several scholars have examined different performance

indicators to evaluate the performance of companies (Nomran & Haron, 2020). Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1987) assessed operational performance, organizational effectiveness, and financial performance as three separate categories of performance. Kaplan and Norton (1996) developed the balanced scorecard method to enhance conventional business performance measurements. The firms' performance can be evaluated using financial and non-financial indicators (Govindarajan & Gupta, 1992; Ittner & Larcker, 1998). Financial performance measures are objective, whereas nonfinancial performance measures are subjective (Venkatraman & Ramanujam, 1987).

2.2. Green Human Capital

GHC is "the sum of employees' pollution prevention or green innovation-related information, competence, expertise, intelligence, inventiveness, and dedication, etc., and is entrenched in people, not firms" (Chen, 2008a). Zhao and Huang (2022) asserted that GHC helps organizations in complying with rigorous international environmental regulations, enhances organizational value, and meets customers' demanding ecological requirements. Furthermore, organizations need to possess ecological information that allows them to identify the appropriate opportunities for making changes to their processes and products to achieve sustainability (Chen, 2008a). Employee's knowledge and skills increase when they realize the company's commitment to sustainability (Tjahjadi et al., 2023). Furthermore, GHC promotes sustainable economic development and improve financial performance (Agyabeng-Mensah & Tang, 2021).

2.3. Green Supply Chain Management

The GSCM was introduced in the 1990s, but its significance became apparent in 2000, as documented in a scientific publication (Samad et al., 2021). Bag et al. (2021) suggest that the environmental stewardship movement of the 1960s can be credited with the development of GSCM. The GSCM concept assumed a conventional form as a novel intellectual endeavor

in the 1990s. As time has progressed, the notion of sustainable supply chain management has evolved further (Dubey et al., 2017). GSCM integrates ecological considerations with inter-organizational sustainable supply chain management techniques, such as logistical operations (Bu et al., 2020). As the concept of GSCM is so broad, providing a standardized explanation for GSCM is challenging due to conflicting definitions in the literature (Schmidt et al., 2017). Several prevalent terms used for GSCM are "sustainable supply network management," "green purchasing and procurement," "supply chain environmental management," and "green logistics and environmental logistics" (Tarigan et al., 2021).

2.4. Green Innovation

GI is innovations in manufacturing processes and products that aim to achieve ecological goals and reduce a product's ecological footprint throughout its life cycle (Lin et al., 2014). GI is an innovative strategy that help organization to reduce pollution, generate greener products, energy saving, recycle and reuse, and manage the environment (Shahzad et al., 2020). Sadly, the prevailing circumstance in underdeveloped nations is a state of disgrace. Innovation-oriented approach enables businesses to reduce pollution and safeguard the environment (Ifrim et al., 2018; Küçükoğlu & Pinar, 2016).

2.5. Organization Green Culture

Organizational culture is a shared system of ideas, beliefs, and values produced by management to change the organization's behavior and attitudes to achieve common company goals (Gürlek & Tuna, 2018). Expanding upon this, OGC is an essential and foundational principle of the organization aimed at safeguarding the environment (Wang, 2019). OGC influences the attitudes and behaviors of team members regarding environmental protection (Chen et al., 2012; Gürlek & Tuna, 2018). Thus, OGC increases environmental sensitivity in an organization and encourages firms to generate green products by integrating green value into

operations (Banerjee et al., 2003; Leonidou et al., 2015).

2.6. Green Human Capital and Firms Performance

The impact of GHC on FP has gained significant attention in recent years. Human capital supports the implementation of green strategies to enhance firm performance, as underscored by the demand for sustainability (Kaplan & Norton, 2004a). It highlights the importance of prioritizing the "green" component of human capital in organizations that adopt environmentally conscious business strategies (Bag & Gupta, 2020). Green human capital significantly impacts environmental performance, provides an organization with a competitive advantage (Chen, 2008b), and enhances firm performance. GHC includes employees' skills, capabilities, and environmental awareness, all of which enhance firm performance. Recent studies have found that green human capital positively influences firm performance, with green market orientation and GSCM serving as mediators of this relationship (Tjahjedi et al., 2023). Similarly, GHC positively influences FP and is mediated by employee environmental awareness (Pratiwi et al., 2025). Moreover, (Agyabeng-Mensah & Tang, 2021) found that green human capital impacts firm financial performance, implying that investments in environmental knowledge and skills can yield significant economic returns. Despite these findings, certain studies indicate that FP is unaffected by GHC (Nureen et al., 2023a), underscoring the need for additional research to clarify the link between GHC and FP. Consequently, the subsequent hypothesis is posited:

H1. GHC significantly impacts FP.

2.7. Green Supply Chain Management and Firms Performance

GSCM is widely acknowledged as a crucial factor in enhancing firm performance. Integrating GSCM to protect the environment enables organizations to reduce raw material costs and increase the utilization of recycled materials, thereby enhancing competitive advantage and

improving firm performance. GSCM can improve FP by facilitating the implementation of sustainable practices (Chu et al., 2017). Choi and Hwang (2015b) proved that adopting GSCM can enhance both financial and environmental performance. Strategies such as GSCM improve economic performance by lowering material acquisition costs, optimizing energy consumption, and decreasing waste treatment and disposal expenses (Zhu et al., 2007). GSCM practices enhance economic performance by decreasing production costs and minimizing energy and waste-related expenses. These enhance the company's reputation and foster customer loyalty, ultimately leading to improved economic performance (Habib et al., 2021). Research indicates that GSCM significantly influences FP, suggesting it may help organizations promote competitiveness and improve financial outcomes over time (Shafique et al., 2017; Tjahjadi et al., 2023). Recent studies have confirmed that GSCM enhances FP in the manufacturing industry (Asamoah et al., 2024). Habib et al. (2021) established that GSCM improves both economic and environmental performance. Nevertheless, companies hold varying opinions on the application of GSCM methods to enhance FP, as firms must understand the components of GSCM to implement the process effectively (Singh et al., 2020). Moreover, few scholars have identified conflicting correlations, indicating that GSCM methods do not directly influence economic performance but may enhance it indirectly (Zhu et al., 2013). A recent research by (Nureen et al., 2023b) found that GSCM does not significantly impact FP. Considering these inconclusive results, additional research is required to elucidate the connection between GSCM and FP. We thus formulated the following hypothesis:

H2. GSCM significantly impacts FP.

2.8. Green Innovation as a mediator

GI is a crucial driver for organizational success (Fernando & Wah, 2017), and its relationship with green human capital and green supply chain management (Ni et al., 2023; Seman et al., 2019; Song et al., 2021) plays an important role in determining firm performance. Several studies

indicate a correlation between GHC and a firm's economic, social, and environmental performance (Aboelmaged & Hashem, 2019); others have found mixed results (Ma et al., 2022; Nureen et al., 2023a), possibly due to the lack of GI. GHC, comprising employees' skills and environmental knowledge, promotes GI, thereby enhancing FP. In turn, green innovation facilitates the development of sustainable products, processes, and services, hence improving FP. Similarly, the relationship between GSCM and FP is unclear, with some studies showing a correlation (Choi & Hwang, 2015; Imran et al., 2021; Tarigan et al., 2021) and others not (Nureen et al., 2023b). This lack of clarity underscores the need to integrate a mediator to clarify the relationships. GI mediates the connection between GSCM and FP, facilitating the development of sustainable supply chains and enhancing reputation and performance. GI reflects a company's ability to pursue market share, strengthen the economy, and improve the socio-cultural environment (Roh et al., 2022). GI mediates links between GHC, GSCM, and FP, enabling firms to mitigate environmental impacts while enhancing performance. We propose that firms that practice green human resources and green supply chain management are more likely to develop green innovation capabilities, thereby achieving sustainable competitive advantage and enhanced performance. Numerous scholars have employed green innovation as a mediator, confirming its role in various contexts. A recent study investigated the impact of organizational green culture and ambidexterity on corporate sustainability and found that green innovation serves as a mediating factor in these relationships (Hafeez et al., 2024). In another study, green innovation mediates between environmental performance and corporate social responsibility (Bonsu et al., 2024). Similarly, Novitasari and Agustia (2021) found that GI mediated the association between GSCM and FP. Furthermore, Seman et al. (2019) confirmed that green supply chain management and environmental performance are mediated by green innovation. Further, Zameer et al. (2022) discovered that green competitive advantage and environmental orientation are mediated by green

innovation. Moreover, Jnaneswar (2024) showed that green innovation mediates the links between human resource management and environmental performance. Consequently, the subsequent hypotheses are posited:

H3a. GI mediates the association between GHC and FP.

H3b. GI mediates the association between GSCM and FP.

2.9. **Organization Green Culture as a moderator**

Organizational culture, defined as a collective system of beliefs, ideas, and values, significantly influences employee behavior and attitude towards achieving organizational goals (Al-Swidi et al., 2021; Wang, 2019). A company's green culture is a crucial element, in which preserving the environment is considered fundamental and established as a core value in the

firm's mission statement (Abbas & Dogan, 2022). This promotes a sense of responsibility among employees, heightening their awareness of environmental concerns and enhancing their work performance (Azhar & Yang, 2022; Lee et al., 2022). A solid OGC not only integrates environmental values and practices but also enhances both environmental and financial performance (Harris & Crane, 2002). By emphasizing eco-environmental values, OGC provides valuable insights for companies to implement environmentally friendly improvements in their operations (Banerjee et al., 2003; Leonidou et al., 2015; Roscoe et al., 2019), such as green supply chain management. OGC can provide advantages to organizations addressing environmental challenges (Al-Swidi et al., 2021). According to Pham et al. (2018), culture may be a valuable tool in helping businesses convert their environmentally proactive objectives into FP.

Figure 1. Theoretical research framework. Source(s): Authors (2026)

The influence of OGC is broad, affecting both the firm and its employees (Gürlek & Tuna, 2018). Employees in an eco-friendly environment are more willing to prioritize environmental concerns, and an organization's capacity to tackle environmental challenges encourages them to

safeguard the environment (Abbas & Dogan, 2022; Azhar & Yang, 2022). The long-term sustainability of a business relies on effectively addressing environmental concerns, such as establishing an environmentally conscious corporate culture (Cherchem, 2017). Recent

studies have demonstrated the moderating role of OGC in various organizational contexts. For instance, OGC moderates the link between green absorptive capacity and green innovation (Qu et al., 2022), green product innovation and artificial intelligence (Lin, 2024), and the association between the circular economy and business financial performance (Kwarteng et al., 2022). This study examines green culture as a moderating variable in the links between green human capital, green supply chain management, and firm performance, acknowledging the significance of culture and its influence on organizational activities. It asserts that green culture enhances the correlation between GHC, GSCM, and FP. Thus, we formulated the following hypotheses:

H4. OGC serves as a moderator between GHC and FP.

H5. OGC serves as a moderator between GSCM and FP.

Figure 1 illustrates the research framework for this study, which assesses the interrelationships among GHC, GSCM, GI, OGC, and FP. The research examines direct, mediating, and moderating effects to evaluate proposed hypotheses. Here, GHC and GSCM are independent variables, GI is a mediating variable, OGC is a moderating variable, and FP is the dependent variable.

3. Research methodologies

3.1. Population and sampling

This quantitative study targeted textile firms in three prominent cities: Multan, Lahore, and Faisalabad. Organizations possessing ISO certificates were deliberately targeted for data collection. This criterion was used to ensure that the chosen textile SMEs possess the requisite knowledge and implement quality and environmental management practices, making them appropriate for the study's emphasis on green practices and performance. Owners and General Managers of these SMEs have been chosen as primary informants, as they are likely to possess essential knowledge and insights regarding their firms' sustainable practices and performance. A purposive sampling method was employed to select firms, targeting specific cities. This method guaranteed participation from all three cities,

ensuring a deeper understanding of the textile sector in these areas. For sample size, a common guideline for factor analysis is to have at least 10 responses per survey item (Nunnally, 1978). It is consistent with the 28 survey items in this study, which require a minimum of 280 responses (10 multiplied by 28 items). According to Hair et al. (2019), a sample size of at least 10 times the estimated parameters is recommended in structural equation modeling.

3.2. Data collection and analysis

A structured questionnaire was administered to Owners and General Managers of textile firms (SMEs) to collect data. The respondents were informed of the study's objectives before the questionnaire was distributed. The questionnaire was disseminated either in person or via email, at the respondents' preference. Furthermore, follow-up reminders and visits were made to ensure a high response percentage. The researchers ensured participants' anonymity, offered voluntary participation, and guaranteed that their information would be used exclusively for scientific research. The data collection phase spanned two months, allowing sufficient time for the participants to provide the required information. A total of six hundred thirty (630) structured questionnaires were sent to participants via offline and online methods. Only three hundred and two (302) questionnaires were returned. The final analysis comprised 284 valid responses after the exclusion of eighteen (18) incomplete or invalid questionnaires. The collected data were examined using SPSS v25 for data cleaning and descriptive statistics, while SmartPLS v4.1 to test the hypotheses. SEM facilitated the analysis of complex connections among variables, comprising mediation and moderation effects.

3.3. Measurement of scales

There are a total of 28 items covering all research constructs. GHC is an independent variable with a four-item scale adopted from prior studies (Chang, 2016; Chen, 2008b). Another independent variable, GSCM, is a ten-item scale adopted from prior research (Tjahjadi et al., 2023).

GSCM comprises two dimensions: internal and external chains. GI is a mediating variable, measured using the four-item scale adopted from a prior study (Chang, 2011). OGC is a moderating variable comprising six items and has been adopted by prior studies (Banerjee, 2002; Fraj et al., 2011). Finally, firm performance is a dependent variable with four items adopted from prior studies (Lin et al., 2013; Yuan et al., 2010), and a self-reported approach is used to assess FP. In this paper, firm performance is measured by market position, sales volume, profit rate, and reputation. This research used a Likert-5-point scale to measure all constructs.

4. Results

4.1. Demographics

The age distribution indicates that a substantial segment of respondents, 116 (40.84%), falls within the 31-36 years age range, while 72 (25.35%) are under 30 years of age. Only 96 respondents (33.80%) are 37 years or older. The majority of respondents have bachelor's degree (37.32%) and a master's degree (46.47%), indicating a highly educated demographic. Regarding professional experience, 39.43% reported 5–6 years, while 25.35% reported over 7 years. The majority of responders (57.74%) were owners/CEOs, whereas (42.25%) occupied the role of general manager. This indicates that the study included key decision-makers in the textile sector. 118 firms (41.54%) had been in operation for 11 to 20 years; while an additional 93 (32.74%) fell into the 21 to 30 years category. The examined companies were predominantly situated in Faisalabad (46.83%), followed by Lahore (30.63%)

and Multan (22.53%), indicating the concentration of the textile sector in these major cities of Punjab, Pakistan.

4.2. Common method bias (CMB)

The study used Harman's single-factor test to evaluate CMB and validate the dataset. The initial factor accounted for 38.093% of the variation, decreasing to 35.894% post-extraction, thereby falling below the critical 50% criterion, suggesting that common method bias was not a substantial issue (Podsakoff et al., 2003). Moreover, variance was distributed among multiple factors, each contributing substantially to the total, suggesting a solid factor structure (Siemsen et al., 2010).

4.3. Descriptive Statistics and Correlation analysis

The mean score (MS) and the standard deviation (SD) of the firm performance (MS = 4.026, SD = 0.740), and green innovation (MS = 3.952, SD = 0.775). Likewise, organizational green culture (MS = 3.964, SD = 0.788), green human capital (MS = 3.991, SD = 0.782), and green supply chain management (MS = 3.912, SD = 0.794). Moreover, Pearson's correlation coefficient is used to examine the relationship between variables and ranges from -1 to +1. A positive value shows a direct association, a negative value implies the opposite, and a zero indicates that no relation exists. The relationship can be weak (0 to 0.3), moderate (0.3 to 0.7), or strong (0.7 or higher) between variables (Turney, 2022). The correlation analysis revealed that all constructs have moderate relationships; see Table 1 for details.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis

Construct	MS	SD	FP	GI	OGC	GHC	GSCM
FP	4.026	0.740	1				
GI	3.952	0.775	.585**	1			
OGC	3.964	0.788	.409**	.407**	1		
GHC	3.991	0.782	.533**	.656**	.307**	1	
GSCM	3.912	0.794	.535**	.605**	.414**	.614**	1

Source(s): Authors (2026)

4.4. Multicollinearity

The multicollinearity assessment examines the relationships among study constructs (Table 3) using the inner model Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). Variables including green innovation (VIF=2.097), organizational green culture (VIF=3.022), green human capital (VIF=1.928), and green supply chain management (VIF=1.928) show no multicollinearity with firm performance, below 5 thresholds (Tirink et al., 2020). These values indicate that the constructs are linked yet maintain adequate distinctiveness. The organizational green culture and its relationship with green human capital (VIF=1.610) and green supply chain management (VIF=1.610) exhibit acceptable levels of multicollinearity, confirming the significance of the interaction term in yielding in-depth analytical insights. Other constructs, such as green human capital and green supply chain management, also demonstrate a suitable level of multicollinearity with green innovation. Such low values verify the independent contribution of these variables to the regression model (Kyriazos & Poga, 2023).

4.5. Statistical analysis

The partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) analysis commences by evaluating the measurement model using the PLS algorithm to confirm that only reliable and valid constructs are employed in the structural path model. This approach is practical for complex models. We employed the reporting guidelines from prior studies (Hair et al., 2019). The measurement model assessment results are presented in Table 4 and 5. The outer loadings for

firm performance range from 0.779 to 0.822, green innovation from 0.806 to 0.827, Organizational green culture from 0.728 to 0.812, green human capital from 0.807 to 0.836, and green supply chain management from 0.702 to 0.781. The results showed that all constructs have suitable factor loadings (above 0.7), so no indicators need to be eliminated. The Cronbach's alpha (α) and composite reliability (CR) values of firm performance (α =0.814, CR=0.877), green innovation (α =0.833, CR=0.889), organizational green culture (α =0.857, CR=0.893), green human capital (α =0.845, CR=0.896), and green supply chain management (α =0.913, CR=0.928) are above 0.7, having suitable construct's reliability. The average variance extracted (AVE) values for firm performance (0.641), green innovation (0.666), organizational green culture (0.581), green human capital (0.682), and green supply chain management (0.562) are all above 0.5, indicating satisfactory levels. Thus, construct validity and reliability have been verified.

4.6. Discriminant validity

The study utilized the heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratio for discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2016). The HTMT ratios for green innovation and firm performance (0.713), organizational green culture and firm performance (0.493), green human capital and firm performance (0.643), and green supply chain management and firm performance (0.620) were below the 0.85 threshold, indicating discriminant validity. Table 3 displays the results of HTMT ratios of study constructs.

Table 2. Reliability and validity

Construct	Items	Loadings	α	CR	AVE
Firm Performance	FP1	0.807	0.814	0.877	0.641
	FP2	0.779			
	FP3	0.796			
	FP4	0.822			
Green Innovation	GI1	0.827	0.833	0.889	0.666
	GI2	0.806			

	GI3	0.818			
	GI4	0.814			
Organizational Green Culture	OGC1	0.751	0.857	0.893	0.581
	OGC2	0.765			
	OGC3	0.812			
	OGC4	0.728			
	OGC5	0.770			
	OGC6	0.744			
Green Human Capital	GHC1	0.828	0.845	0.896	0.682
	GHC2	0.836			
	GHC3	0.807			
	GHC4	0.831			
Green Supply Chain Management	GSCM1	0.735	0.913	0.928	0.562
	GSCM2	0.712			
	GSCM3	0.763			
	GSCM4	0.759			
	GSCM5	0.741			
	GSCM6	0.702			
	GSCM7	0.781			
	GSCM8	0.756			
	GSCM9	0.768			
	GSCM10	0.776			

Source(s): Authors (2026)

Table 3. Heterotrait–monotrait (HTMT) ratios

No.	Constructs	1	2	3	4	5
1	Firm Performance	-				
2	Green Innovation	0.713	-			
3	Organizational Green Culture	0.493	0.484	-		
4	Green Human Capital	0.643	0.785	0.361	-	
5	Green Supply Chain Management	0.620	0.694	0.468	0.697	-

Source(s): Authors (2026)

4.7. Empirical results

The findings validate the suitability of the measurement model for conducting a structural model. To test the structural model's hypothesized associations (Figure 2; Table 4), SmartPLS-4.1 used bootstrapping across 10,000 samples. The study evaluates GHC significantly and positively impacts FP, accepting hypothesis H1. H2 predicts that GSCM is positively related to FP. The findings reveal that GSCM has a positive effect on FP, accepting hypothesis H2. The study used recommendations from Preacher and Hayes

(2008) to examine the mediation of GI between the link of GHC, GSCM and FP. The study examined the mediation of GI in the relationships among GHC, GSCM, and FP, as hypothesized in H3a and H3b. For hypothesis H3a, the impact of GHC on FP without a mediating effect was significant; with the inclusion of mediation, the direct and indirect effects were also substantial (see Figure 2). The findings confirm hypothesis H3a by demonstrating that GI partially mediates GHC and FP links. For hypothesis H3b, the impact of GSCM on FP without a mediating effect was

significant; with the inclusion of mediation, the direct and indirect effects were also significant (see Figure 2). The results confirm that GI partially mediates the GSCM-FP relationships. The results show that all direct and indirect effects are significant; GI mediates the relationships among GHC, GSCM, and FP, supporting H3a and H3b (Preacher & Hayes, 2008). Further, OGC

strengthens the relationships between the GHC-FP and GSCM-FP, thereby accepting H4 and H5. Figure 3 and 4 shows slope analysis to better understand the moderating effect. It showed that at higher OGC levels, the impact of GHC and GSCM on FP is much stronger than at lower OGC levels.

Table 4. Hypotheses testing

Hypotheses	Relationship	β	SD	t-value	p-value	Result
H1	GHC -> FP	0.348	0.072	4.829	0.000	Accepted
H2	GSCM -> FP	0.311	0.078	3.989	0.000	Accepted
H3a	GHC -> GI -> FP	0.156	0.039	3.994	0.000	Accepted
H3b	GSCM -> GI -> FP	0.113	0.034	3.340	0.001	Accepted
H4	OGC x GHC -> FP	0.158	0.065	2.439	0.015	Accepted
H5	OGC x GSCM -> FP	0.132	0.065	2.044	0.041	Accepted

Source(s): Authors (2026)

Figure 2. Structural model. Source(s): Authors (2026)

4.8. Model’s predictive power and predictive relevance

The next step is to evaluate R^2 and Q^2 for the model’s predictive power and predictive relevance (Table 5), as these are essential metrics in SEM. Cohen (1998) classified R^2 values as weak (0.02), moderate (0.15), and large 0.35). The results show that green human capital and green supply chain management explained 50.3% of the variation in green innovation. Moreover, 53.7% of the change in firm performance is explained by organizational green culture, green innovation, green human

capital, and green supply chain management. Firm performance ($R^2 = 0.537$) and green innovation ($R^2 = 0.503$) demonstrate significant explanatory power, confirming a robust correlation between exogenous and endogenous variables. Hence, the R^2 values of all study variables validate predictive accuracy. Moreover, Stone- Geisser’s Q^2 values obtained by the PLSpredict function; values higher than zero imply good predictive relevance (Geisser, 1974; Stone, 1974). The Q^2 values of 0.434 and 0.489 for firm performance and green innovation indicate the model has predictive relevance.

Table 5. Model’s predictive power (R^2) and predictive relevance (Q^2)

Constructs	R-square	R-square adjusted	Q^2 predict
Firm performance	0.537	0.428	0.434
Green innovation	0.503	0.499	0.489

Source(s): Authors (2026)

5. Discussion

The statistical analysis shows that GHC has a significant impact on FP ($\beta = 0.348$, $t = 4.829$, $p = 0.000$), confirming hypothesis H1. The results are similar to recent studies that confirmed a significant impact of GHC on FP (Agyabeng-Mensah & Tang, 2021; Muafi et al., 2021a). Nureen et al. (2023a) concluded that GHC has no statistically significant effect on FP. Human capital is essential for supporting the execution of a strategy (Kaplan & Norton, 2004b; Talapatra et al., 2022). A recent study confirmed that internal and external knowledge sharing impacts economic, environmental and social performance. Organizations that adopt environmentally conscious business strategies must prioritize their

human capital's "green" component (Bag & Gupta, 2020).

GSCM exerts a substantial positive impact on FP ($\beta = 0.311$, $t = 3.989$, $p = 0.000$), thereby supporting hypothesis H2. The outcomes of this investigation are consistent with the conclusions drawn in previous research (Choi & Hwang, 2015a; Tarigan et al., 2021). Novitasari and Agustia (2021) discovered that GSCM had no discernible effect on FP. GSCM has ability to improve FP by facilitating the implementation of practices related to managing environment (Chu et al., 2017). GSCM facilitates organizations to enhance financial performance and competitiveness over time (Shafique et al., 2017). Firms must apply the various aspects of GSCM to get better results (Singh et al., 2020)

Figure 3. Interaction plot of OGC×GHC on FP. Source(s): Authors (2026)

Hypothesis H3a examines the mediation of GI in the connection between GHC and FP. Significant direct effects of GHC and FP were observed ($\beta = 0.193$, $t = 2.870$, $p = 0.004$). The indirect relationships between GHC and GI ($\beta = 0.455$, $t = 6.165$, $p = 0.000$) and the similarity between GI and FP ($\beta = 0.342$, $t = 5.130$, $p = 0.000$) were statistically significant. The results confirmed hypothesis H3a by demonstrating that GI partially mediates the relationship between GHC and FP ($\beta = 0.156$, $t = 3.994$, $p = 0.000$). The results align with a prior investigation by Muafi et al. (2021a). Hypothesis H3b investigates how GI act as mediator in the association between GSCM and FP. For hypothesis H3b, a significant direct effects of GSCM and FP were observed ($\beta = 0.198$, $t = 2.766$, $p = 0.006$). There were also statistically substantial indirect relationships between GSCM and GI ($\beta = 0.332$, $t = 4.669$, $p = 0.000$) and GI and FP ($\beta = 0.342$, $t = 5.130$, $p = 0.000$). The study confirmed hypothesis H3b by finding that GI partially mediates the relationship between GSCM and FP ($\beta = 0.113$, $t = 3.340$, $p = 0.001$). The outcome aligns with prior studies (Seman et al.,

2019) that discovered GI mediates between GSCM and FP. Novitasari and Agustia (2021) found that GI mediated the association between GSCM and FP. The firm's ecological objectives and environmental management endeavors rely heavily on human resources (Munawar et al., 2022). GHC impacts environmental performance and confers a competitive edge to an organization (Chen, 2008b). Ni et al. (2023) found a positive association between GHC and GI across three different cultures (Pakistan, India, and Bangladesh). GSCM has a favorable impact on GI (Novitasari & Agustia, 2021). This concept showed that GSCM is very important to a firm's GI. This interaction helps firms to improve manufacturing processes and product development, and ecological regulations (Le et al., 2022). Seman et al. (2019) found a significant link between GSCM and GI. Moreover, Li et al. (2022) illustrated that reactive GSCM has a lesser impact on GI than proactive GSCM. Additionally, the influence of the GSCM on GI varies depending on the learning environment.

Figure 4. Interaction plot of OGC×GSCM on FP. Source(s): Authors (2026)

The increasing demand for eco-friendly products is a significant impetus for the company to implement GI strategies (Gupta & Barua, 2018). The success of an organization is linked to implementation of green innovation (Fernando & Wah, 2017). GI significantly improves operational, financial, and environmental performance (Xue et al., 2019). GI significantly improves sustainability (economic and ecological) and FP (Maldonado-Guzmán et al., 2023). Nonetheless, Seman et al. (2019) discovered that GI has the potential to reduce the financial performance and raise organizational expenditures (Kraus et al., 2020). El-Kassar and Singh (2019) revealed that non-GI firms have a more robust FP than GI firms. Thus, GI is key to success for organizations (Fernando & Wah, 2017).

A moderation analysis examined whether OGC moderates the GHC-FP and GSCM-FP relationships. Hypothesis 4 found that OGC significantly and positively moderates the association of GHC-FP ($\beta = 0.158$, $t = 2.439$, $p = 0.015$), supporting hypothesis H4. Figure 3 show that GHC affects FP more when OGC is high (1

SD above the mean). High OGC will strengthen or increase the simple slope corresponding to GHC and FP. Low OGC (1 SD below the mean) reduces the effect. Results showed that GHC improved FP more with higher OGC. Another moderation analysis examined whether OGC moderates the GSCM-FP relationships. Hypothesis 5 revealed that OGC significantly and positively moderates the association of GSCM-FP ($\beta = 0.132$, $t = 2.044$, $p = 0.041$), supporting hypothesis H5. Figure 4 show that GSCM affects FP more when OGC is high (1 SD above the mean). Low OGC (1 SD below the mean) reduces the effect. OGC impacts both the firm and its employees (Gürlek & Tuna, 2018). Akuma et al. (2025) found that OGC moderates the relationships between green strategy and financial performance. (Qu et al., 2022) found that OGC moderates green absorptive capacity-GI links.

5.1. Theoretical Implications

The present investigation has yielded noteworthy theoretical advancements, providing novel results. The existing literature found a contradictory connection between GHC and FP (Nureen et al.,

2023a; Tjahjadi et al., 2023). It also addresses the need for a clearer understanding of the relationship, as highlighted by scholars (Agyabeng-Mensah & Tang, 2021; Muafi et al., 2021b; Tjahjadi et al., 2023). We discovered a direct and significant association between GHC and FP as per our proposed hypothesis. Therefore, our research offers concrete evidence in favor of the claims made by NRBVT (Hart, 1995) and confirms that GHC is a valuable asset for organizations, helps to achieve a competitive edge, and improves FP (Hart & Dowell, 2011). Moreover, we explored the contradictory link of GSCM with FP, as discussed by prior studies (Choi & Hwang, 2015a; Nureen et al., 2023b). We aim to provide further clarification on the nature of this relationship, as requested by scholars such as Choi and Hwang (2015a) and Tarigan et al. (2021). Our research indicates a direct and significant link between GSCM and FP. Our study empirically supports the propositions of NRBVT (Hart, 1995) and confirms that GSCM can effectively address ecological issues and improve performance. Thus findings indicate that GHC and GSCM have positive, significant effects on FP, suggesting that both are necessary to improve FP. Further, we discovered that GI mediates GHC, GSCM, and FP. Analyzing GI as a mediator is a fresh theoretical approach in a developing country with limited research. Findings indicate that GI is pivotal for Pakistani textile firms. The applications of GI enable GHC and GSCM practices to exert a more significant influence on FP. This implies that by implementing GI and higher levels of GSCM and GHC, textile firms in developing nations can enhance their FP directly and indirectly.

The study contributes to NRBVT literature by taking the perspective of developing countries and demonstrating that GI remains an essential performance component. This investigation explored the neglected role of organizational green culture as a moderator between GHC, GSCM, and FP. The statistical analysis revealed that a solid green culture within an organization enhances GHC, GSCM, and FP relationship. This study contributes to the existing literature on greening and sustainability. The study also advances

NRBVT theory in academia and research. By examining Pakistan's textile industry, the study expands existing knowledge. The investigated variables are all crucial to improving firm performance. The current study enhances the existing knowledge base by focusing on the textile industry, a significant sector of Pakistan's economy. The study contributes significantly to the academic and research communities concerning the NRBVT as a theoretical development. The NRBVT posits that firms can increase FP and sustain competitiveness by addressing environmental challenges. Natural resources as well as skills improve firms' long-term performance. Furthermore, FP is also linked to corporate competencies, environmental resources, and pollution control techniques (Barney, 2000). In conclusion, it is indisputable that organizations require GHC, GSCM, GI, and OGC to attain a competitive edge and improve FP.

5.2. Managerial Implications

Our proposed research framework is predicated on utilizing the impacts of GHC and GSCM on FP. It also examined the mediating role of GI and the moderating role of OGC in the links between GHC-FP and GSCM-FP. The research provides industry practitioners and decision-makers with several practical implications regarding the path to greening organizations and leveraging FP. The dynamic global business environment compels organizations to adopt a proactive stance toward environmental surveillance and sustainability to enhance operational effectiveness. In doing so, managers are advised to proactively implement ecological strategies such as GHC, GSCM, GI, and OGC within their organizations to enhance FP. Organizations must focus on their green talent by hiring, compensation, training, and other procedural systems. Managers must steadfastly resolve to utilize and develop effective information systems to preserve their GHC. Employees are more committed to attaining environmental goals when their organizations have exceptional ecological programs. By adopting GSCM, textile firms can enhance quality, ensure clean productivity, and boost industrial competitiveness. Organizations must consistently

try to improve and update their GHC and GSCM. The study provides a reminder to management that GI promotes sustainable growth and provides organizations with a "first mover advantage" (Soewarno et al., 2019). OGC is a fundamental organization-building element critical for GHC and GSCM, which increases FP. Additionally, the research advises managers that GI and OGC are critical factors in enhancing FP and should be implemented and energized to their full capacity. To maintain the satisfaction of their most important stakeholders, managers and leaders must devote significant organizational time and resources to enhancing their GHC, GSCM, GI, and OGC capabilities. Failure to prioritize these environmentally friendly considerations could adversely affect an organization.

5.3. Conclusion

Employing the "natural resource-based view theory," the study examined the nexus among GHC, GSCM, GI, OGC, and FP. Primary data were collected from owners and managers associated with the textile industry in Pakistan. To analyze the responses of 284 participants, SPSS v25 and SmartPLS v4.1 were used. Descriptive statistics and Herman's single-factor tests were performed utilizing SPSS v25. PLS-SEM analysis was performed with the help of SmartPLS v4.1. Findings indicate that GHC and GSCM exert a favorable effect on FP. Additionally; findings confirm that GI serves as a partial mediator among GHC, GSCM, and FP relationships. Moreover, the research confirmed that OGC moderates the GHC-FP and GSCM-FP relationships positively and statistically significantly. The results emphasize the significance of investing in green human capital, implementing sustainable supply chain methods, green innovation and establishing a green organizational culture to enhance performance. This study offers significant insights for textile companies and regulators seeking to enhance sustainability and competitiveness. Pakistani manufacturing firms must prioritize green practices (such as GHC, GSCM, GI, and OGC) as these are critical factors for firm performance.

5.4. Limitations and Recommendations

The study has specific constraints that subsequent researchers may resolve. The current investigation is being carried out in a specific domestic setting, namely the textile sector of Punjab province, Pakistan. Our results need more generalizability to different cultural contexts. To examine how outcomes vary across industries, subsequent researchers may use this methodology to study other manufacturing industries, such as food manufacturing organizations. In the future, scholars may utilize sampling methods other than purposive sampling to collect data. The study was conducted in Pakistan, a nation renowned for its distinct cultural milieu. Subsequently, scholars may investigate this framework in other countries. Future investigations could involve comparative studies. The data was obtained from a few cities in Punjab, including Multan, Faisalabad, and Lahore. The researchers can extend this framework to other cities or provinces. Future researchers may enhance the sample size to conduct this framework. The study evaluates how GI mediates, and OGC moderates the link between GHC-FP and GSCM-FP. Future researchers may analyze this model by using green knowledge management as an independent variable, environmental agility as a mediator, and environmental strategy, employee empowerment, and green transformational leadership as moderators of the proposed relationships. Additionally, our study may be subject to specific limitations due to its cross-sectional design. In the future, longitudinal data may be utilized to investigate the interrelationships among the constructs in greater depth.

References

- Abbas, J., & Dogan, E. (2022). The impacts of organizational green culture and corporate social responsibility on employees' responsible behaviour towards the society. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(40), 60024-60034.

- Abeyssekara, N., Wang, H., & Kuruppuarachchi, D. (2019). Effect of supply-chain resilience on firm performance and competitive advantage: A study of the Sri Lankan apparel industry. *Business Process Management Journal*, 25(7), 1673-1695.
- Aboelmaged, M., & Hashem, G. (2019). Absorptive capacity and green innovation adoption in SMEs: The mediating effects of sustainable organisational capabilities. *Journal of cleaner production*, 220, 853-863.
- Adenle, A. A., Azadi, H., & Arbiol, J. (2015). Global assessment of technological innovation for climate change adaptation and mitigation in developing world. *Journal of environmental management*, 161, 261-275.
- Agyabeng-Mensah, Y., & Tang, L. (2021). The relationship among green human capital, green logistics practices, green competitiveness, social performance and financial performance. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 32(7), 1377-1398.
- Akuma, J., Akude, D., Kwaning, E., & Asiama, K. (2025). Green marketing practices and financial performance of manufacturing firms: The moderating role of organizational culture. *Multidisciplinary Reviews*, 8(1), 2025017-2025017.
- Al-Swidi, A. K., Gelaidan, H. M., & Saleh, R. M. (2021). The joint impact of green human resource management, leadership and organizational culture on employees' green behaviour and organisational environmental performance. *Journal of cleaner production*, 316, 128112.
- Asamoah, D., Acquah, I. N., Nuertey, D., Agyei-Owusu, B., & Kumi, C. A. (2024). Unpacking the role of green absorptive capacity in the relationship between green supply chain management practices and firm performance. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 31(8), 2793-2818.
- Asghar, B., Wasim, A., Qazi, U., & Rasool, A. (2020). Financial and non-financial practices driving sustainable firm performance: Evidence from banking sector of developing countries. *Sustainability*, 12(15), 6164.
- Awan, U., Khattak, A., & Kraslawski, A. (2019). Corporate social responsibility (CSR) priorities in the small and medium enterprises (SMEs) of the industrial sector of Sialkot, Pakistan. *Corporate social responsibility in the manufacturing and services sectors*, 267-278.
- Awan, U., Kraslawski, A., & Huiskonen, J. (2017). Understanding the relationship between stakeholder pressure and sustainability performance in manufacturing firms in Pakistan. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 11, 768-777.
- Azhar, A., & Yang, K. (2022). Examining the influence of transformational leadership and green culture on pro-environmental behaviors: Empirical evidence from Florida city governments. *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, 42(4), 738-759.
- Bag, S., & Gupta, S. (2020). Examining the effect of green human capital availability in adoption of reverse logistics and remanufacturing operations performance. *International Journal of Manpower*, 41(7), 1097-1117.
- Bag, S., Gupta, S., Kumar, S., & Sivarajah, U. (2021). Role of technological dimensions of green supply chain management practices on firm performance. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 34(1), 1-27.
- Banerjee, S. B. (2002). Corporate environmentalism: The construct and its measurement. *Journal of business research*, 55(3), 177-191.
- Banerjee, S. B., Iyer, E. S., & Kashyap, R. K. (2003). Corporate environmentalism: Antecedents and influence of industry type. *Journal of marketing*, 67(2), 106-122.
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of management*, 17(1), 99-120.

- Barney, J. B. (2000). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. In *Economics meets sociology in strategic management* (pp. 203-227). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Bonsu, M. O.-A., Guo, Y., & Zhu, X. (2024). Does green innovation mediate corporate social responsibility and environmental performance? Empirical evidence from emerging markets. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 25(2), 221-239.
- Bu, X., Dang, W. V., Wang, J., & Liu, Q. (2020). Environmental orientation, green supply chain management, and firm performance: empirical evidence from Chinese small and medium-sized enterprises. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(4), 1199.
- Chang, C.-H. (2011). The influence of corporate environmental ethics on competitive advantage: The mediation role of green innovation. *Journal of business ethics*, 104, 361-370.
- Chang, C. H. (2016). The determinants of green product innovation performance. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 23(2), 65-76.
- Chen, Y.-S. (2008a). The driver of green innovation and green image-green core competence. *Journal of business ethics*, 81, 531-543.
- Chen, Y.-S. (2008b). The positive effect of green intellectual capital on competitive advantages of firms. *Journal of business ethics*, 77, 271-286.
- Chen, Y. S., Chang, C. H., & Wu, F. S. (2012). Origins of green innovations: the differences between proactive and reactive green innovations. *Management Decision*, 50(3), 368-398.
- Cherchem, N. (2017). The relationship between organizational culture and entrepreneurial orientation in family firms: does generational involvement matter? *Journal of family business strategy*, 8(2), 87-98.
- Choi, D., & Hwang, T. (2015a). The impact of green supply chain management practices on firm performance: the role of collaborative capability. *Operations Management Research*, 8, 69-83.
- Choi, D., & Hwang, T. (2015b). The impact of green supply chain management practices on firm performance: the role of collaborative capability: D. Choi, T. Hwang. *Operations Management Research*, 8(3), 69-83.
- Chu, S. H., Yang, H., Lee, M., & Park, S. (2017). The impact of institutional pressures on green supply chain management and firm performance: Top management roles and social capital. *Sustainability*, 9(5), 764.
- Cohen, J. (1998). *Statistical Power Analysis for The Behavioral Sciences*. Howick Place. In: London: Routledge.
- Dubey, R., Gunasekaran, A., & Papadopoulos, T. (2017). Green supply chain management: theoretical framework and further research directions. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 24(1), 184-218.
- El-Kassar, A.-N., & Singh, S. K. (2019). Green innovation and organizational performance: The influence of big data and the moderating role of management commitment and HR practices. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 144, 483-498.
- Fernando, Y., & Wah, W. X. (2017). The impact of eco-innovation drivers on environmental performance: Empirical results from the green technology sector in Malaysia. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 12, 27-43.
- Fraj, E., Martínez, E., & Matute, J. (2011). Green marketing strategy and the firm's performance: the moderating role of environmental culture. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 19(4), 339-355.
- Geisser, S. (1974). A predictive approach to the random effect model. *Biometrika*, 61(1), 101-107.
- Govindarajan, V., & Gupta, A. K. (1992). *Linking control systems to business unit strategy: impact on performance*. Springer.

- Guo, J., Zhou, Y., Ali, S., Shahzad, U., & Cui, L. (2021). Exploring the role of green innovation and investment in energy for environmental quality: An empirical appraisal from provincial data of China. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 292, 112779.
- Gupta, H., & Barua, M. K. (2018). A grey DEMATEL-based approach for modeling enablers of green innovation in manufacturing organizations. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 25, 9556-9578.
- Gürlek, M., & Tuna, M. (2018). Reinforcing competitive advantage through green organizational culture and green innovation. *The service industries journal*, 38(7-8), 467-491.
- Habib, M. A., Bao, Y., Nabi, N., Dulal, M., Asha, A. A., & Islam, M. (2021). Impact of strategic orientations on the implementation of green supply chain management practices and sustainable firm performance. *Sustainability*, 13(1), 340.
- Hafeez, M., Yasin, I., Zawawi, D., Odilova, S., & Bataineh, H. A. (2024). Unleashing the power of green innovations: the role of organizational ambidexterity and green culture in achieving corporate sustainability. *European Journal of Innovation Management*. <https://doi.org/https://doi:10.1108/ejim-04-2023-0274>
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European business review*, 31(1), 2-24.
- Halim, E. H., Mustika, G., Sari, R. N., Anugerah, R., & Mohd-Sanusi, Z. (2017). Corporate governance practices and financial performance: The mediating effect of risk management committee at manufacturing firms. *Journal of International Studies*, 10(4).
- Harris, L. C., & Crane, A. (2002). The greening of organizational culture: Management views on the depth, degree and diffusion of change. *Journal of organizational change management*, 15(3), 214-234.
- Hart, S. L. (1995). A natural-resource-based view of the firm. *Academy of management review*, 20(4), 986-1014.
- Hart, S. L., & Dowell, G. (2011). Invited editorial: A natural-resource-based view of the firm: Fifteen years after. *Journal of management*, 37(5), 1464-1479.
- Henseler, J., Hubona, G., & Ray, P. A. (2016). Using PLS path modeling in new technology research: updated guidelines. *Industrial management & data systems*, 116(1), 2-20.
- Huang, J.-W., & Li, Y.-H. (2017). Green innovation and performance: The view of organizational capability and social reciprocity. *Journal of business ethics*, 145, 309-324.
- Ifrim, A. M., Stoenică, I. C., Petrescu, A. G., & Bilcan, F. R. (2018). The impact of green innovation on organizational performance: Evidence from Romanian SMEs. *Academic journal of economic studies*, 4(1), 82-88.
- Imran, M., & Jingzu, G. (2022). Green organizational culture, organizational performance, green innovation, environmental performance: A mediation-moderation model. *Journal of Asia-Pacific Business*, 23(2), 161-182.
- Ittner, C. D., & Larcker, D. F. (1998). Innovations in performance measurement: Trends and research implications. *Journal of management accounting research*, 10, 205.
- Jnaneswar, K. (2024). Demystifying the relationships among green HRM, green work engagement, green innovation and environmental performance: a serial mediation model. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 20(6), 1193-1213. <https://doi.org/https://Doi:10.1108/SRJ-08-2023-0457>
- Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (1996). Using the balanced scorecard as a strategic management system.
- Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (2004a). Measuring the strategic readiness of intangible assets. *Harvard Business Review*, 82(2), 52-63.

- Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (2004b). *Strategy maps: Converting intangible assets into tangible outcomes*. Harvard Business Press.
- Khan, A. N., Mehmood, K., & Kwan, H. K. (2024). Green knowledge management: A key driver of green technology innovation and sustainable performance in the construction organizations. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 9(1), 100455.
- Khan, S. A. R., Yu, Z., Golpira, H., Sharif, A., & Mardani, A. (2021). A state-of-the-art review and meta-analysis on sustainable supply chain management: Future research directions. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 278, 123357.
- Kraus, S., Rehman, S. U., & García, F. J. S. (2020). Corporate social responsibility and environmental performance: The mediating role of environmental strategy and green innovation. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 160, 120262.
- Küçükoğlu, M. T., & Pınar, R. İ. (2016). The mediating role of green organizational culture between sustainability and green Innovation: A research in Turkish companies.
- Kwarteng, A., Simpson, S. N. Y., & Agyenim-Boateng, C. (2022). The effects of circular economy initiative implementation on business performance: the moderating role of organizational culture. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 18(7), 1311-1341.
- Kyriazos, T., & Poga, M. (2023). Dealing with multicollinearity in factor analysis: the problem, detections, and solutions. *Open Journal of Statistics*, 13(3), 404-424.
- Le, T. T., Vo, X. V., & Venkatesh, V. (2022). Role of green innovation and supply chain management in driving sustainable corporate performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 374, 133875.
- Lee, C.-C., Wang, C.-W., & Ho, S.-J. (2022). The dimension of green economy: Culture viewpoint. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 74, 122-138.
- Leonidou, L. C., Fotiadis, T. A., Christodoulides, P., Spyropoulou, S., & Katsikeas, C. S. (2015). Environmentally friendly export business strategy: Its determinants and effects on competitive advantage and performance. *International Business Review*, 24(5), 798-811.
- Li, L., Shan, S., Dai, J., Che, W., & Shou, Y. (2022). The impact of green supply chain management on green innovation: A meta-analysis from the inter-organizational learning perspective. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 250, 108622.
- Lin, J., Zeng, Y., Wu, S., & Luo, X. R. . (2024). How does artificial intelligence affect the environmental performance of organizations? The role of green innovation and green culture. *Information & Management*, 61(2). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2024.103924>
- Lin, R.-J., Chen, R.-H., & Huang, F.-H. (2014). Green innovation in the automobile industry. *Industrial management & data systems*, 114(6), 886-903.
- Lin, R.-J., Tan, K.-H., & Geng, Y. (2013). Market demand, green product innovation, and firm performance: evidence from Vietnam motorcycle industry. *Journal of cleaner production*, 40, 101-107.
- Liu, J., Liu, Y., & Yang, L. (2020). Uncovering the influence mechanism between top management support and green procurement: The effect of green training. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 251, 119674.
- Ma, X., Ock, Y.-S., Wu, F., & Zhang, Z. (2022). The effect of internal control on green innovation: corporate environmental investment as a mediator. *Sustainability*, 14(3), 1755.

- Maldonado-Guzmán, G., Garza-Reyes, J. A., & Pinzón-Castro, S. Y. (2023). Green innovation and firm performance: the mediating role of sustainability in the automotive industry. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*(ahead-of-print).
- Muafi, M., Norek, T., & Siswanti, Y. (2021a). The influence of green human capital on business performance: The mediation role of innovation activity. The Importance of New Technologies and Entrepreneurship in Business Development: In The Context of Economic Diversity in Developing Countries: The Impact of New Technologies and Entrepreneurship on Business Development,
- Muafi, M., Norek, T., & Siswanti, Y. (2021b). The influence of green human capital on business performance: The mediation role of innovation activity. In The Importance of New Technologies and Entrepreneurship in Business Development: In The Context of Economic Diversity in Developing Countries: The Impact of New Technologies and Entrepreneurship on Business Development (pp. 1371-1380). Springer International Publishing.,
- Munawar, S., Yousaf, H. Q., Ahmed, M., & Rehman, S. (2022). Effects of green human resource management on green innovation through green human capital, environmental knowledge, and managerial environmental concern. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 52, 141-150.
- Ni, L., Ahmad, S. F., Alshammari, T. O., Liang, H., Alsanie, G., Irshad, M., Alyafi-AlZahri, R., BinSaeed, R. H., Al-Abyadh, M. H. A., & Bakir, S. M. d. M. A. (2023). The role of environmental regulation and green human capital towards sustainable development: The mediating role of green innovation and industry upgradation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 421, 138497.
- Nomran, N. M., & Haron, R. (2020). A systematic literature review on Shari'ah governance mechanism and firm performance in Islamic banking. *Islamic Economic Studies*, 27(2), 91-123.
- Novitasari, M., & Agustia, D. (2021). Green supply chain management and firm performance: The mediating effect of green innovation. *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 14(2), 391-403.
- Nunnally, J. C. (1978). Psychometric theory. In: McGraw-hill.
- Nureen, N., Liu, D., Irfan, M., Malik, M., & Awan, U. (2023a). Nexuses among green supply chain management, green human capital, managerial environmental knowledge, and firm performance: evidence from a developing country. *Sustainability*, 15(6), 5597.
- Nureen, N., Sun, H., Irfan, M., Nuta, A. C., & Malik, M. (2023b). Digital transformation: fresh insights to implement green supply chain management, eco-technological innovation, and collaborative capability in manufacturing sector of an emerging economy. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(32), 78168-78181.
- Onubi, H. O., Carpio, M., & Hassan, A. S. (2024). Job satisfaction in green construction projects: antecedent roles of green work climate, pro-environmental construction practice and green human capital. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 31(5), 1857-1878.
- Pham, N. T., Phan, Q. P. T., Tučková, Z., Vo, N., & Nguyen, L. H. (2018). Enhancing the organizational citizenship behavior for the environment: the roles of green training and organizational culture. *Management & Marketing*, 13(4), 1174-1189.
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Lee, J.-Y., & Podsakoff, N. P. (2003). Common method biases in behavioral research: a critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *Journal of applied psychology*, 88(5), 879.

- Pratiwi, I., Saefudin, A., Sari, G. I., Maliki, B. I., & Nuryano, U. W. (2025). Green human capital and organizational performance: The role of employee environmental awareness and sustainable innovation in achieving organizational sustainability. *Innovation and Green Development*, 4(3), 100244.
- Preacher, K. J., & Hayes, A. F. (2008). Asymptotic and resampling strategies for assessing and comparing indirect effects in multiple mediator models. *Behavior research methods*, 40(3), 879-891.
- Qu, X., Khan, A., Yahya, S., Zafar, A. U., & Shahzad, M. (2022). Green core competencies to prompt green absorptive capacity and bolster green innovation: the moderating role of organization's green culture. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 65(3), 536-561.
- Rehman, S. U., Kraus, S., Shah, S. A., Khanin, D., & Mahto, R. V. (2021). Analyzing the relationship between green innovation and environmental performance in large manufacturing firms. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 163, 120481.
- Roh, T., Noh, J., Oh, Y., & Park, K.-S. (2022). Structural relationships of a firm's green strategies for environmental performance: The roles of green supply chain management and green marketing innovation. *Journal of cleaner production*, 356, 131877.
- Roscoe, S., Subramanian, N., Jabbour, C. J., & Chong, T. (2019). Green human resource management and the enablers of green organisational culture: Enhancing a firm's environmental performance for sustainable development. *Business strategy and the Environment*, 28(5), 737-749.
- Samad, S. (2018). Examining the effects of environmental strategy and competitive advantage on business performance. *Management Science Letters*, 8(9), 891-902.
- Samad, S., Nilashi, M., Almulihi, A., Alrizq, M., Alghamdi, A., Mohd, S., Ahmadi, H., & Azhar, S. N. F. S. (2021). Green Supply Chain Management practices and impact on firm performance: The moderating effect of collaborative capability. *Technology in Society*, 67, 101766.
- Schmidt, C. G., Foerstl, K., & Schaltenbrand, B. (2017). The supply chain position paradox: green practices and firm performance. *Journal of supply chain management*, 53(1), 3-25.
- Seman, N. A. A., Govindan, K., Mardani, A., Zakuan, N., Saman, M. Z. M., Hooker, R. E., & Ozkul, S. (2019). The mediating effect of green innovation on the relationship between green supply chain management and environmental performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 229, 115-127.
- Shafique, M., Asghar, M., & Rahman, H. (2017). The impact of green supply chain management practices on performance: Moderating role of institutional pressure with mediating effect of green innovation. *Business, Management and Economics Engineering*, 15(1), 91-108.
- Shahzad, M., Qu, Y., Zafar, A. U., Rehman, S. U., & Islam, T. (2020). Exploring the influence of knowledge management process on corporate sustainable performance through green innovation. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 24(9), 2079-2106.
- Sharma, G. D., Kraus, S., Srivastava, M., Chopra, R., & Kallmuenzer, A. (2022). The changing role of innovation for crisis management in times of COVID-19: An integrative literature review. *Journal of innovation & knowledge*, 7(4), 100281.
- Shoaib, M., Abbas, Z., Yousaf, M., Zámečník, R., Ahmed, J., & Saqib, S. (2021). The role of GHRM practices towards organizational commitment: A mediation analysis of green human capital. *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1), 1870798.

- Shu, C., Zhou, K. Z., Xiao, Y., & Gao, S. (2016). How green management influences product innovation in China: The role of institutional benefits. *Journal of business ethics*, 133, 471-485.
- Siemsen, E., Roth, A., & Oliveira, P. (2010). Common method bias in regression models with linear, quadratic, and interaction effects. *Organizational research methods*, 13(3), 456-476.
- Singh, S. K., Del Giudice, M., Chierici, R., & Graziano, D. (2020). Green innovation and environmental performance: The role of green transformational leadership and green human resource management. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 150, 119762.
- Soewarno, N., Tjahjadi, B., & Fithrianti, F. (2019). Green innovation strategy and green innovation: The roles of green organizational identity and environmental organizational legitimacy. *Management Decision*, 57(11), 3061-3078.
- Song, W., & Yu, H. (2018). Green innovation strategy and green innovation: The roles of green creativity and green organizational identity. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 25(2), 135-150.
- Song, W., Yu, H., & Xu, H. (2021). Effects of green human resource management and managerial environmental concern on green innovation. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 24(3), 951-967.
- Stone, M. (1974). Cross-validatory choice and assessment of statistical predictions. *Journal of the royal statistical society: Series B (Methodological)*, 36(2), 111-133.
- Szilagyi, A. D. (1981). Management and performance. (No Title).
- Talapatra, S., Santos, G., & Gaine, A. (2022). FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN EATERY BUSINESS- AN EMPIRICAL STUDY FROM BANGLADESH. *International Journal for Quality Research*, 16(1).
- Tang, M., Walsh, G., Lerner, D., Fitza, M. A., & Li, Q. (2018). Green innovation, managerial concern and firm performance: An empirical study. *Business strategy and the Environment*, 27(1), 39-51.
- Tarigan, Z. J. H., Siagian, H., & Jie, F. (2021). Impact of enhanced Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) on firm performance through green supply chain management. *Sustainability*, 13(8), 4358.
- Tırınk, C., Abacı, S. H., & Onder, H. (2020). Comparison of ridge regression and least squares methods in the presence of multicollinearity for body measurements in saanen kids. *Journal of the Institute of Science and Technology*, 10(2), 1429-1437.
- Tjahjadi, B., Agastya, I. B. G. A., Soewarno, N., & Adyantari, A. (2023). Green human capital readiness and business performance: do green market orientation and green supply chain management matter? *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 30(10), 3884-3905.
- Turney, S. (2022). Pearson correlation coefficient (R): guide & examples. Scribbr. In.
- Venkatraman, N., & Ramanujam, V. (1987). Measurement of business economic performance: An examination of method convergence. *Journal of management*, 13(1), 109-122.
- Wang, C.-H. (2019). How organizational green culture influences green performance and competitive advantage: The mediating role of green innovation. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 30(4), 666-683.
- Xue, M., Boadu, F., & Xie, Y. (2019). The penetration of green innovation on firm performance: Effects of absorptive capacity and managerial environmental concern. *Sustainability*, 11(9), 2455.
- Yu, W., Ramanathan, R., & Nath, P. (2017). Environmental pressures and performance: An analysis of the roles of environmental innovation strategy and marketing capability. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 117, 160-169.

- Yuan, L., Zhongfeng, S., & Yi, L. (2010). Can strategic flexibility help firms profit from product innovation? *Technovation*, 30(5-6), 300-309.
- Zailani, S., Jeyaraman, K., Vengadasan, G., & Premkumar, R. (2012). Sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) in Malaysia: A survey. *International journal of production economics*, 140(1), 330-340.
- Zameer, H., Wang, Y., Yasmeen, H., & Mubarak, S. (2022). Green innovation as a mediator in the impact of business analytics and environmental orientation on green competitive advantage. *Management Decision*, 60(2), 488-507.
- Zhao, W., & Huang, L. (2022). The impact of green transformational leadership, green HRM, green innovation and organizational support on the sustainable business performance: Evidence from China. *Economic research-Ekonomska istraživanja*, 35(1), 6121-6141.
- Zhu, Q., Sarkis, J., & Lai, K.-h. (2007). Green supply chain management: pressures, practices and performance within the Chinese automobile industry. *Journal of cleaner production*, 15(11-12), 1041-1052.
- Zhu, Q., Sarkis, J., & Lai, K.-h. (2013). Institutional-based antecedents and performance outcomes of internal and external green supply chain management practices. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 19(2), 106-117.

